

VOL. 47

OCTOBER 2023

SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL SURVEY OF ARACHNIDA

SANSA Newsletter 47

SANSA NEWSLETTER

UPDATED NATIONAL SPIDER SPECIES LIST AVAILABLE SOON

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) was initiated in 1997 with the main aim of documenting the arachnid fauna of South Africa at a national level. The First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (FASSA) was published in 2010 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) where 70 families, 463 genera, and 2003 species were listed.

Now, 12 years later, a new checklist of 2285 spider species and subspecies, belonging to 488 genera and 72 families recorded from South Africa, has been compiled for publication (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, under review). Distribution data were extracted from the South African National Survey of Arachnida database and more than 200 taxonomic revisions up to the end of December 2022.

Global and provincial distributions, endemism, and conservation assessment using IUCN criteria are provided for each species. A total of 1185 spp. are endemic to South Africa (51.9%), 129 spp. (5.6%) are of special concern, and 689 spp. (30.2%) are Data Deficient (DD), while 15 species were described without exact locality data. Most species (1458 spp., 63.8%) are widely distributed with no known threats and are of Least Concern. Of the species recorded, 57.6% (1316 spp.) are known from both sexes, and 23 spp. (1.0%) were only described from juveniles. Salticidae is the most species-rich family, with 353 spp., followed by Gnaphosidae (202 spp.), Thomisidae (145 spp.), and Araneidae (112 spp.), while 10 families are represented by a single species.

Species richness peaks in the KwaZulu-Natal province (1037 spp., 45.4% of South African species), followed by the Western Cape province (938 spp., 41.1%) and Limpopo (912 spp., 39.9%). Spatial bias in sampling is visually assessed and suggests that the Northern Cape and North West provinces are underrepresented in the database.

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. *First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Technical Report 2010 version 1 1160 pp. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628809>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LOTZ L.N., BOOYSEN R., STEENKAMP R.C. & FOORD S.H. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of South Africa. *Checklist* (under review).

IN THIS ISSUE

Updated National Spider Species list	1
New books and guide now available	2
New publication: <i>Seothyra</i> webs	3
New publication: Nephilidae rank resurrected	3
New project: Spider survey in macadamia	4
New project: Spider survey Waterberg	5
New project: Spider survey – Umgeni River	6
New project: Spider survey in pine and forest	7
New project: BUGS	8
Araneopathogenic fungus	9
Recent publications	10
New publication: New <i>Stasimopus</i> spp.	10
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i>	11-13
<i>Thyene natalii</i>	14-17
<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i>	18-20
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i>	21-23
Spiders of Groenkloof Nature Reserve	24-32
Spiders of Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve	33-42

EDITORIAL COMMITTEE

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman
dippenaaransie@gmail.com

Ruan Booysen
booysenr@ufs.ac.za

Leon Lotz
leonlotz57@gmail.com

Rudi Steenkamp
rudolphsteinkampf@gmail.com

Stefan Foord
stefan@foord.co

Zenodo Repository
<https://zenodo.org/communities/sansa/>

NEW BOOKS

Thoroughly revised and updated, this long-awaited new edition of *Field Guide to the Spiders of South Africa* remains the most comprehensive guide to South African spiders published to date. It features over 780 of the more common spider species encountered in the veld and in homes and gardens, as well as representative species from some of the rarer spider families.

- 'Quick Keys' to the 72 South African spider families provide a useful starting point to identification.
- Succinct genus and species accounts cover identifying characteristics, breeding, behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.
- Colour photographs and/or illustrations as well as distribution maps support each entry.
- Introductory chapter discusses spider morphology, spider life cycle, the functions of silk, as well as spider collection techniques.
- Section on venom identifies species that pose a danger to humans, unpacks neurotoxic and cytotoxic venom, and details the symptoms and treatment of spider bites.

Publication date: August 2023

ISBN: 9781775847977

ePub: 9781775847984

Format: 210 x 148 mm

Extent: 400 pages

Text: ± 110 000 words

Images: Full-colour photographs

Language: English

Cover: Softcover

Imprint: Struik Nature

Retail price: R480

This is an exciting time in the study of spiders in South Africa as biologists are beginning to recognise the importance of spiders in the functioning of a healthy ecosystem. They are important predators in all terrestrial ecosystems and can be regarded as the best friends of reserve managers, gardeners, and farmers in sustainable agriculture.

This book provides information on the spiders of the Fernkloof Nature Reserve (FNR). The reserve is situated in the Fynbos Biome. Despite the relative small coverage of only 6.7% in South Africa, the Fynbos Biome is regarded as a priority hotspot for conservation. This is the first checklist compiled for FNR and presently lists 47 spider families represented by 235 species. In FNR the free-living ground dwellers are more abundant (40%), than the web dwellers (33%) with the plant dwellers in the minority (23%).

BOOK AVAILABLE FROM: Victor Hamilton-Attwell
vicattwell@sonicmail.co.za

Publication date: September 2023

ISBN: ISBN 978-0-6397-7866-2 (Printed book)

Format: 210 x 148 mm

Extent: 120 pages

Images: Full-colour photographs

Language: English

Cover: Softcover

Imprint: Hermanus Botanical Society

Retail price: R300.00

NEW PHOTO GUIDE

CORINNIDAE GUIDE NOW AVAILABLE

Corinnidae is a moderately large cosmopolitan family known from 76 genera and 848 species (World Spider Catalog, 2023). The number of genera and species known from South Africa has increased considerably during recent years. Presently, 15 genera represented by 44 species are known from South Africa, of which 23 species (52%) are South African endemics. Twenty-eight of the species (63%) have a wide range and are of Least Concern, whereas 11 species are Data Deficient. Only five species of the genus *Hortipes* have been identified as species of special concern due to their restricted distributions. A key to the South African genera of Corinnidae is provided.

The guide can be downloaded from the World Spider Catalog and Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sansa/>

NEW PUBLICATION

HADDAD C.R., CODRON D., VENTER C. & BOOYSEN R. 2023 The unique buckspoor webs of *Seothyra* optimize silk use and capture efficiency. *Journal of Arid Environments* 218 (2023) 105057.

The full article can be downloaded from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2023.105057>

ABSTRACT: Buckspoor-web spiders of the genus *Seothyra* are Southern African endemics predominantly occurring in arid and semi-arid habitats. They have evolved a uniquely shaped web, comprising a burrow in which the spider rests, linked to a slightly asymmetrical two- to four-lobed web on the soil surface. We investigated the association between three web parameters (periphery, surface area, and compactness) and three body size parameters (carapace length, total length, and mass) of *S. schreineri* in central South Africa. Using a novel pixel-seeding image analysis, we were able to accurately determine the surface area of individual webs and compare their area: periphery ratio with that of hypothetical circular webs with the same perimeter length to determine the isoperimetric quotient of each. Isoperimetric quotients across all life stages indicated an average reduction of approximately 25% in silk investment, being highest in juveniles (~35%). Web periphery was related to web area by a power function, but web area increased at a progressively faster rate than periphery with increasing web size, indicating that larger spiders build less compact webs; i.e., web shape is affected by spider size. Web area and periphery scaled positively and allometrically with the three measures of spider body size, but no significant effect of body size on web compactness was found. We conclude that the unique shape of *Seothyra* webs evolved as a mechanism to optimize the periphery and concurrently reduce the surface area, thereby enhancing their potential to capture prey and reduce silk investment in the web structure.

Figures 1–4. *Seothyra schreineri*. 1. Female. 2. Male, 3-4. Webs of an adult female with four lobes (4) and a subadult female with three lobes (3) at Bankfontein, South Africa. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

NEW PUBLICATION

KUNTNER M., ČANDEK K., GREGORIČ M., TURK E., HAMILTON C.A., CHAMBERLAND L., STARRETT J., CHENG R.C., CODDINGTON J.A., AGNARSSON I. & BOND J.E. 2023. Increasing information content and diagnosability in family-level classifications. *Systematic Biology* 72(4): 964–971.

From abstract: “In spider classification, families are the highest rank that is systematically catalogued, and *incertae sedis* is not allowed. Consequently, it is important that family level taxa be well defined and informative. We revisit the classification problem of Orbipurae, an unranked supra familial clade containing the spider families Nephilidae, Phonognathidae, and Araneidae *sensu stricto*. We argue that, to maximize diagnosability, information content, conservation utility, and practical taxonomic considerations, this “splitting” scheme is superior to its recently proposed alternative, which lumps these families together as Araneidae *sensu lato*. We propose to redefine Araneidae and recognize a monogeneric spider family, Paraplectanoididae fam. nov. to accommodate the depauperate lineage”.

HOW THIS AFFECTS TAXA FROM SOUTH AFRICA

FAMILY NEPHILIDAE Simon, 1894 Family Rank Resurrected

Composition. — Nephilidae contains the genera *Clitaetra* Simon, 1889; *Herennia* Thorell, 1877; *Indoetra* Kuntner 2006; *Nephila* Leach, 1815; *Nephilengys* L. Koch, 1872; *Nephilingis* Kuntner 2013 and *Trichonephila* Dahl, 1911

FAMILY PHONOGNATHIDAE Simon, 1894 New Rank

Spiders of the family Phonognathidae construct two-dimensional orb webs whose hub is modified into a retreat, either constructed with silk (*Leviellus*) or by using a rolled-up leaf (*Phonognatha*, *Artiphex*, *Deliochus*, and *Zygiella*). Note: Presently *Zygiella x-notata* is listed from South Africa.

NEW PROJECT: University of Venda

MACADAMIA FARMS IN SOUTPANSBERG SPRAY LESS, HAVE MORE ABUNDANT AND DIVERSE SPIDER ASSEMBLAGES ,AND PRODUCE BETER-QUALITY NUTS

What happens to spiders in macadamia orchards that are managed differently and embedded in contrasting matrices? We attempted to answer this question by sampling spiders along an elevational transect on the southern slopes of the eastern Soutpansberg, a major macadamia production region.

We sampled spiders using a thermal fogger on six farms stratified along the transect in July 2021. We also processed all other invertebrates. Remarkably, spiders were the most abundant invertebrate group (2223 spiders), twice as abundant as the next order, Hemiptera (bugs). Incidentally, bugs include the most important pest species on macadamia. We recorded a total 86 spider species, which included a new Thomisidae species in the genus *Tmarus* (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. New *Tmarus* species for which the first adult female was found in this study.

Most species (85%) were plant wanderers, and 90% of the 10 most abundant species were wanderers. The two dominant species were a *Clubiona* cf *pongolensis* (756) (Fig. 2) followed by the salticid *Thyene natalii* (273) (Fig. 3). Both of these species were two orders of magnitude more abundant on farms that did not spray or sprayed very little pesticide. *Chresiona* sp. 1 was the third most abundant species, and the only species in the top 10 species considered as ground and plant wandering. They tended to be more abundant in the orchards that received more pesticide, suggesting that their ground-dwelling habitats shield them against pesticide applications. Exploratory analysis also suggests that the increased use of pesticides is linked to decreased nut quality metrics. In contrast, these metrics are positively associated with general invertebrate diversity and spider diversity. Furthermore, abundance of spiders in macadamia suggests that they might not only be important in pest control but also as food for other predators.

CONTACTS: Stefan Foord (stefan@foord.co) and Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (dippenaaransie@gmail.com)

Figures 2–5. Some of the spider species commonly found on the macadamia trees. 2. *Clubiona* cf *pongolensis*. 3. *Thyene natalii*. 4. *Thyene coccineovittata*. 5. *Oxytate leruthi*. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

STUDENT PROJECT: University of KwaZulu-Natal

ARTHROPOD DIVERSITY PATTERNS ALONG ELEVATIONAL GRADIENTS, WATERBERG MOUNTAINS IN LIMPOPO PROVINCE

The estimation of global species has been an issue for over 250 years. However, recent climate warming has caused changes in species distribution as well as species abundance, and the extent of this effect is unclear. Recent studies have documented a decline in the occurrence of arthropods and other insects, a shift in their geographical ranges, as well as a decline in taxonomic richness and the exact underlying mechanisms. The impact of this is proving hard to investigate because we lack baseline data. We also lack historical information about the occurrence of arthropods, particularly on African mountains.

In this respect, it is important to understand many ecological and biogeographical issues such as the origin and distribution of biodiversity, through firstly documenting what species occur in defined ecosystems and their diversity patterns (alpha diversity) and secondly quantifying the extent of change in community composition (beta diversity) along elevational gradients. Elevational gradients allow us to infer how assemblages are subject to change due to gradual alteration in climate and disturbances since they are strongly associated with changes in both temperature and precipitation. The Waterberg mountains are an ideal study site. They are very diverse ancient mountains with very little information about the occurrence of arthropods compared to vertebrates.

This study addresses three objectives:

- To create ant, spider, and beetle inventories for nine game reserves across the Waterberg mountains.
- To investigate the drivers of species richness on the Waterberg mountains.
- To model assemblage turnover and community composition.

Nine areas of interest were identified on the Waterberg mountains (Marekele National Park, Masebe Nature Reserve, Welgevonden Game Reserve, Ka'Ingo Private Reserve, Jembisa, Swebeswebe, Lindani Game and Lodges, Laphalala North, and Leobo Private Reserve). From these areas a total of 56 sites were sampled across the mountains. The sites were at different elevations (1000 masl to 1800 masl) and geographical distances. The north and south aspect of the mountains were considered, and sampling was done in open and closed habitats. The sampling took place in September 2022 and January 2023. Here, a standardised pitfall trapping method was used, vegetation data were recorded, and soil samples were collected.

A total of 1825 specimens were sampled and 127 species were identified in Pretoria by Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. The voucher specimens are housed in collections in Pretoria.

CONTACTS: *Caroline Kunene, Stefan Foord, and Caswell Munyai (munyaic2@ukzn.ac.za)*

Activities in the Waterberg mountains showing the different localities sampled.

STUDENT PROJECT: University of KwaZulu-Natal**THE RESPONSE OF RIPARIAN ARTHROPODS TO FLOW CHANGES ALONG THE UMGENI RIVER, KWAZULU-NATAL**

Riparian zones are transitional areas between land and fresh-water systems such as lakes, wetlands, and rivers. They are found adjacent to water bodies and are relatively small landscapes compared to upland ecosystems. Nonetheless, they have unique features due to their soil, vegetation properties, and disturbance regimes, making them complex and dynamic. These habitats offer various ecosystem services, such as enhancing water quality by filtering out pollutants, riparian vegetation stabilising soil and therefore preventing soil erosion. They can also be resilient to the impact of climate change as the vegetation can capture and store carbon dioxide for photosynthesis, thereby counteracting greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, they host a wide variety of plants and animals.

Some of the dominant animals found in riparian zones are arthropods, including spiders. They connect riparian zone, fresh-water systems, and upland ecosystems by linking the terrestrial-aquatic food web as a food source and predators of other animals. As a dominant predatory group, spiders control populations of various other invertebrates and, to a limited extent, vertebrate species. They are also sensitive to environmental changes, making them ideal indicators to assess, manage, and restore riparian zones. However, a few studies have documented the consequences of various anthropogenic and natural disturbances along riparian zones on arthropods. Therefore, this study aims to investigate how river flow changes influence the biodiversity of terrestrial arthropods along the Umgeni River in KwaZulu-Natal.

The current study therefore determines whether there is variation in the biodiversity of riparian arthropods in relation to flow changes and how taxonomic and functional diversity varies along different sites of the Umgeni River. The river is sampled downstream using pitfall traps, starting from Umgenipoort Research Facility, where the river begins, flowing through the city of Pietermaritzburg to Durban, where it flows through various land use including urbanisation, river damming, and industrialisation, then into the Indian Ocean.

The wet season sampling occurred in March 2023, while the upcoming sampling will occur in September 2023. We anticipate species turnover, whereby disturbance-sensitive species are expected to be found upstream; in contrast, disturbance-tolerant species will be expected to be downstream as the river passes through different land uses.

The study will positively impact the communities that rely on the Umgeni River. For instance, an emphasis on protecting riparian zones and their biodiversity will ensure that people have access to clean water and improved sanitation. Moreover, initiatives to restore threatened riparian zones will promote employment opportunities for the adjacent communities. Equally important, the sustainability of arthropods will guarantee sufficient food for fish, increasing the fish population, which the communities can rely on as a source of food, alleviating hunger. Through community engagement with local people, this project will also engage the communities on the benefits of riparian zones and how to use them sustainably.

Asande Hadebe sampling along the Umgeni River in the Umgenipoort Research Facility in KwaZulu-Natal. Photo credit: Caswell Munyai.

STUDENT PROJECT: University of KwaZulu-Natal

Drivers of arthropod diversity in monoculture timber plantations and natural forests

Forests are valued for their biodiversity and the provision of ecosystem services for human livelihood. They store carbon dioxide while producing oxygen, which regulates temperatures and purifies the atmosphere. They create job opportunities and supply fuel for local inhabitants. To increase timber production in South Africa, timber forests are planted on land that previously contained native vegetation, such as grasslands. This is particularly prominent in the Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal, and Eastern Cape provinces. In South Africa, timber plantations cover a total area of 1.2 million hectares of land across the country. Therefore, faunal communities inhabiting natural vegetation remain at high risk of population declines and extinctions due to habitat loss.

As timber plantations are now part of the South African landscape, it is necessary to investigate their effect on biodiversity and determine their potential to contribute to conservation. In agroecosystems such as timber plantations, spiders are one of the essential predators, naturally preventing pest outbreaks. They are often used to assess forest quality.

The current study therefore answers three specific questions:

- How do arthropod communities vary between a native forest and *Pinus* and *Eucalyptus* monoculture plantations?
- What are the specific local environmental factors that influence the observed trends?
- What are the specific species associated with the three habitats?

Over two seasons, sampling was done at the Umgeniport Research Facility in the KwaZulu-Natal Midlands. Arthropods were collected using pitfall traps from a native forest and two types of monoculture plantations, the *Pinus* plantation and the *Eucalyptus* plantation. The local environmental variables measured were temperature, horizontal habitat elements such as the presence of rocks, leaf litter, vegetation, vertical vegetation complexity, and soil characteristics.

A total of 888 specimens were sampled and 30 species identified in Pretoria by Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman. The voucher specimens will be housed in collections in Pretoria.

CONTACTS: *Thembekile Mthimunye* and *Caswell Munyai* (munyaic2@ukzn.ac.za)

The Umgeniport Research Facility in the KwaZulu-Natal Midlands.

Thembekile Mthimunye sampling in the pine plantation.

One of the species sampled at the Umgeniport Research Facility: Trachelidae *Spinotrachelas montanus*. Photo credit: Peter Webb, from Wakefield Farm.

Another species sampled at the Umgeniport Research Facility: Phx-elididae *Vidole helicigyna*. Photo credit: Peter Webb, from Wakefield Farm.

NEW PROJECT: BUGS

Biodiversity under global pressures in soils: BUGS in the Kalahari

The mitigation of current ecological challenges, in particular the impacts of climate change on biodiversity, requires robust predictions of responses of natural populations across the food web to global change. Climate change, in particular increasingly extreme temperatures, has already been shown to have severe adverse effects on animals in arid systems, including the Kalahari. Much of the research on animal responses to increasing climate extremes in the Kalahari has resulted from the long-term monitoring of small carnivores and birds at the Kalahari Research Station. Many of these species, such as meerkats (*Suricata suricatta*), yellow mongoose (*Cynictis penicillata*), or pied bblers (*Turdoides bicolor*) rely on soil fauna as their main food source, and any adverse effects of climate change on their population dynamics likely occurs via changes in food abundance. However, despite strong evidence that invertebrates are in decline globally, their abundances have not been studied extensively in drylands, including the Kalahari – and we know little about how changes in soil-fauna abundances and biomass scale up to affect upper trophic levels.

The **BUGS project**, spearheaded by Maria Paniw and Walter Jubber, aims to enhance our comprehension of spatiotemporal changes in soil-fauna abundances. Operating at the Kalahari Research Station, Maria and Walter have strategically deployed 100 pitfall traps in sites distinguished by different land use types (natural, low grazing, and high grazing), which will allow us to understand how climate and land use interact to affect soil fauna. In each site, 10 traps are located on transects along an elevation gradient and are monitored every 14 days for 48 hours (Figures 1–3). All captured invertebrates are morphologically classified at least to family level (and species level wherever possible) with the valuable collaboration with various experts in the relevant fields. Furthermore, all samples are weighted to determine biomass. Concurrently, the project monitors vegetation and microclimate at the sites.

The project took off successfully in August 2023, and several different species were already collected. The results of this project will create an important baseline to understand variation not only of soil-fauna biodiversity, but also potential effects of this variation on the carnivores that depend on this diversity and are monitored at the same sites.

Figures 1–3. Strategic deployment and setup of funnel pitfall traps at the relevant sites, located along an elevation gradient. Photo credits: Maria Paniw.

CONTACTS: Maria Paniw, Spanish National Research Council (maria.paniw@ebd.csic.es) and Walter Ralph Jubber, Kalahari Research Trust, University of the Witwatersrand (wrajubber@gmail.com)

ARANEOPATHOGENIC FUNGUS FROM NORTH PARK RESERVE, QUEENSBURGH

A request in the March 1992 Spider Club newsletter for information on spider victims of pathogenic fungi led, over the years, to the finding of several specimens (including insects) killed by parasitic fungi in the Queensburgh area, near Durban, and a few were submitted to the Mycology Department of the Plant Protection Research Institute in Pretoria. Not all the fungus specimens could be identified.

The most recent find was made on 22 August 2023, when a fungus was observed to have completely enveloped a small spider and attached it to the underside of the leaf of a turkey-berry tree (*Canthium inerme*: Rubiaceae) growing in moderate shade on the fringe of a stand of riparian forest at North Park Nature Reserve, Northdene, Queensburgh. It was found at a height of about 2.5 m.

The bright lemon-yellow fungus-encrusted spider measured 5 mm (8 mm with extended forelegs) x 4 mm x 3 mm and little could be distinguished of the victim (Figs 1 and 2). From its general morphology, barred extended forelegs (the only portion free of fungal overgrowth), and prominent abdominal tubercles, the spider seemed to belong to the Araneidae. Initially it was thought that only one pair of tubercles was present but a second, smaller pair may be present posteriorly but are almost completely masked by the fungus. If the second pair of tubercles can be unambiguously observed, then the spider victim may be a species similar to a curious specimen photographed under similar environmental conditions, but under a metre from the ground, in September 2017 (Fig. 3).

At that time, and based on the photograph, Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman commented: "This is one of our 'mystery spiders'. We have named it *Araneid morpho sp. 6*. We have sampled them also from Kloof and Mkuzi but we do not know even the genus. We have several strange *Araneidae* genera. I will search further!" (email correspondence: 28 September 2017). Since then, further thought has gone into the problem and "I spent some time trying again to find a name for this species. It might be a new *Cyclosa* sp. (email correspondence: 1 September 2023). The fungus specimen will be donated to the ARC Plant Health and Protection for identification and voucher specimens will be placed in their fungus collection.

Identified victims of araneopathogenic fungi are scarce; in part because their identifying features are completely, or almost completely, masked by the fungus. At present, two specimens in the ARC-PHP collection have the salticid victims almost certainly identified. These will be described and illustrated in a forthcoming note.

Figure 1: Araneidae spider enveloped by an araneopathogenic fungus beneath leaf of *Canthium inerme* (L.f.) Kuntze (Rubiaceae). Dorsal view.

Figure 2. Postero-lateral view showing a pair of prominent abdominal tubercles. 22 August 2023.

Fig. 3. The suspected victim species: Araneidae. "possibly *Cyclosa* sp." Length: 3.5 mm. Abdomen 2.0 x 2.0 mm. North Park Nature Reserve, Northdene, Queensburgh.

CONTACT AND PHOTOS: *Hugh Heron hughheronescombe@gmail.com*)

Images of the same species photographed by Peter Webb and Bruce Blake in Kloof. Could this maybe be a *Cyclosa* sp.? When comparing it with drawings of *Cyclosa* spp. by Levi 1999: 372–343.

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

BRANDT S., SOLE C. & LYLE R. 2023. An integrative taxonomy of the genus *Stasimopus* Simon 1892 (Araneae: Mygalomorphae) of the Karoo with the description of nine new species and a *Stasimopus maraisi* Hewitt 1914 male. *Zootaxa* 5341(1): 1–60. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5341.1.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. *Field guide to the spiders of South Africa*. Struik Nature, Cape Town, 400 pp.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & BUCK J. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Gondwana Private Game Reserve, in the Western Cape, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137378>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape province, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8135774>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LOTZ L.N., BOOYSEN R., STEENKAMP R. & HADDAD C.R. 2023. A review of the synanthropic spiders from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 35–43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137426>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2023. More on the spotted jumping spider *Thyene coccineovittata* (Simon, 1886) in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 10–12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137448>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2023. Additional information on the brown crab spider *Thomisus scrupeus* (Simon, 1886) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 13–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137430>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., PAGEL K. & BUCK J. 2023. Notes on the crab spider *Phaenopoma nigropunctatum* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 46: 7–9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137402>.

HADDAD C.R., CODRON D., VENTER C. & BOOYSEN R. 2023 The unique buckspeer webs of *Seothyra* optimize silk use and capture efficiency. *Journal of Arid Environments* 218 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2023.105057>.

HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L. N. 2023. *The Corinnidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 72 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.8300753.

HAMILTON-ATTWELL V.L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. *Spiders of Fernkloof Nature Reserve*. Hermanus Botanical Society, Hermanus.

KUNTNER M., ČANDEK K., GREGORIČ M., TURK E., HAMILTON C.A., CHAMBERLAND L., STARRETT J., CHENG R.C., CODDINGTON J.A., AGNARSSON I. & BOND J.E. 2023. Increasing information content and diagnosability in family-level classifications. *Systematic Biology* 72(4): 964–971.

NEW PUBLICATION

BRANDT S., SOLE C. & LYLE R. 2023. An integrative taxonomy of the genus *Stasimopus* Simon 1892 (Araneae: Mygalomorphae) of the Karoo with the description of nine new species and a *Stasimopus maraisi* Hewitt 1914 male. *Zootaxa* 5341(1): 1–60. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5341.1.1.

ABSTRACT: The genus *Stasimopus* Simon 1892 is endemic to Southern Africa, but is historically largely understudied. This paper provides a taxonomic revision for the *Stasimopus* species of the Karoo region of South Africa and includes the description of nine new species (*S. dylani* sp. nov., *S. finni* sp. nov., *S. hamartia* sp. nov., *S. ignis* sp. nov., *S. karoensis* sp. nov., *S. malesociatus* sp. nov., *S. tera* sp. nov., *S. theaei* sp. nov., and *S. venterstadensis* sp. nov.). A description of the genetically matched *S. maraisi* Hewitt 1914 male is provided. The original *S. maraisi* male is designated to its own new species (*S. malesociatus* sp. nov.). An identification key is provided for species occurring in the Karoo region. This is the first integrative taxonomy for the genus that includes morphological, geometric morphometric as well as genetic data.

Figures 1–4: 1. *Stasimopus ignis* female. 2. *Stasimopus ignis* male. 3. *Stasimopus tera* female. 4. *Stasimopus theaei* female.

CONTACT: Robin Lyle (LyleR@arc.agric.za)

Notes on the crab spider *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942 in South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & P. Webb†²

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSA Gauteng team member (deceased)

Abstract: The crab spider *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942 has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa the species was regularly sampled from agroecosystems and is recognised as one of five agrobionts that play an important role as natural control agents of pest species. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens and notes on their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, biodiversity, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) large numbers of Thomisidae were sampled and presently 143 species from 37 genera are recorded from South Africa.

The genus *Misumenops* F.O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900 contains 55 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2023). Some of these species were formerly listed in the genera *Diaea*, *Misumena*, and *Synema*. *Misumenops* is sometimes regarded as a genus of convenience, intermediate between *Misumena* and *Diaea*. Gertsch (1939), however, considered *Misumenops* as being representative of a group of spiders quite different from related genera.

All the aforementioned genera are listed under Misumenini from the diagnoses provided by Simon (1895) and Mello-Leitão (1929), which are chiefly based on the eye pattern and some other somatic characters. The minor differences between them are difficult to observe and therefore the identification and generic placement of the species have been confusing at best.

A study of Palearctic, Oriental, and some African, Pacific, and American species (Lehtinen, 1993; 2004) revealed that the majority of species assigned to *Misumenops* are not related to the type species and belong elsewhere. Considering the lack of proper drawings of the type species and principles applied to the taxonomy of the Misumenini, it is not surprising that the concept of *Misumenops* is quite vague. Lehtinen and Marusik (2008) redefine *Misumenops* and numerous New World species were moved to other genera.

Misumenops is not well represented in the Afrotropical region and only two species have been recorded to date, of which one was formerly placed in the genus *Misumena*. Lessert (1919) regarded *Misumenops* as a subgenus of *Misumena* as they resemble *Misumena* in shape and colour but differ in having many erect setae on the body and legs (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

In this paper, we provide more information on the crab spider that we presently recognise as *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942. It is an African endemic described from Guinea and reported from several countries throughout Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2023). This paper aims to collate all information on the species, including the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens, their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status, with notes on their presence in crops and agrobiont status. The data were gathered during SANSA surveys.

Figures 1–2. *Misumenops rubrodecoratus*. 1. Female lateral view. 2. Female dorsal view. 3. Male anterior view. Photo credits: 1. Vida vd Walt. 2–3. Peter Webb.

Figures 4–9. *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* female showing the colour variations. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

TAXONOMY

Misumenops rubrodecoratus Millot, 1942

Misumenops rubrodecorata Millot, 1942: 37; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983: 51.

Misumenops rubrodecoratus Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 51, 52.

Description: Size: TL females 4.4–6.7 mm. Female: yellow to pale green (green fades in alcohol to yellow), sometimes with red or brown patterns or lines on carapace and abdomen; legs I and II sometimes banded with red or brown (Figs 4–9). Carapace as wide as long, low and slightly convex; surface clothed with numerous erect spiniform setae (Fig. 2); clypeus vertical, with four pairs of long primary setae on margin. Eyes in two recurved rows; lateral eyes larger than median eyes, situated on conjoined tubercles (Fig. 1). Sternum heart-shaped. Abdomen round in dorsal view; flattened, clothed with numerous erect spiniform setae. Legs: anterior two pairs approximately equal in length and thickness, longer and stronger than posterior pairs; pro-lateral surface of femora I and II with strong setae; ventral surface of tibiae and metatarsi with double row of macrosetae. Epigyne shown in Figs 10–11.

Male (Figs 3 & 13–14). Size: males 1.5–4.0 mm. Male differs structurally from the female as follows: setae on body, especially those on abdomen, longer and more numerous; legs longer and thinner, macrosetae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II weakly developed. Male palp shown in Fig. 12.

Figures 10–14. *Misumenops rubrodecoratus*. 10–11. Female genitalia. 12. Male palp. 13–14. Male habitus. Photo credits: 10–12. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). 13–14. Peter Webb.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

The species was described by Millot (1942) from Kindia, Guinea. During a revision by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983), specimens from different museums were studied and new records from Mali, Namibia, South Africa, Sudan, Upper Volta, and Zimbabwe were recorded.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

The species is widely distributed throughout South Africa (Map 1). Detailed locality data with coordinates can be found in Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020 (pp. 51–52).

Map 1. Known distribution of *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* Millot, 1942.

LIFESTYLE

Misumenops rubrodecoratus is a very common thomisid species recorded from South Africa. Adults are collected throughout the year, except in the winter months. They are active during the day and prey on a variety of small invertebrates, potentially playing an important role in the natural control of pests such as aphids, red spider mites, and thrips. They inhabit grass, shrubs, flowers, and trees, and have been sampled from all the floral biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

It was one of the 44 thomisid species sampled from crops in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013), and sampled from avocado, citrus, cotton, kenaf, lucerne, macadamia, maize, pecans, pine plantations, pistachio, pumpkin, sugar cane, sunflower, strawberries, and tomatoes.

In citrus orchards, of the 18 crab spider species collected, *M. rubrodecoratus* was the most abundant. Van den Berg *et al.* (1992) observed that they prey on adult citrus psylla. Feeding experiments indicated that they also prey on aphids, red spider mites, and thrips.

In cotton fields, *M. rubrodecoratus* was the most abundant species collected in five cotton-growing areas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). On cotton, the species is mostly found on leaves and stems, near bracts of cotton plants, as well as hiding under dry leaves on the ground (Van den Berg, 1989). In the laboratory they preyed on red spider mites, the first two larval stages of *Helicoverpa armigera*, as well as on aphids (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999).

Of the arboreal spiders collected over a 12-month period from three macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa, *M. rubrodecoratus* was the most abundant thomisid species sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001).

REFERENCES

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1983. The spider genera *Misumena*, *Misumenops*, *Runcinia* and *Thomisus* (Araneae: Thomisidae) of southern Africa. *Entomology Memoir, Department of Agriculture Republic of South Africa* 55: 1–66.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020. *The Thomisidae of South Africa. Part 1 A-Mo*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 62 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7513274

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: a review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG, A. 1999. Spiders in South African cotton fields: species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 5: 93–103.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG M.A. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2001. Spiders in macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa: species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 7: 36–46.

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.

GERTSCH W.J. 1939. A revision of the typical crab-spiders (Misumeninae) of America north of Mexico. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* 76: 277–442.

HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 97–122.

LEHTINEN P.T. 1993. Polynesian Thomisidae - a meeting of Old and New World groups. *Memoirs of the Queensland Museum* 33: 585–591.

LEHTINEN P.T. 2004. Taxonomic notes on the Misumenini (Araneae: Thomisidae: Thomisinae), primarily from the Palaearctic and Oriental regions. In: Logunov, D. V. & D. Penney (eds.) *European Arachnology 2003*.

LEHTINEN P.T. & MARUSIK Y.M. 2008. A redefinition of *Misumenops* F.O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1900 (Araneae, Thomisidae) and review of the New World species. *Bulletin of the British Arachnological Society* 14(4): 173–198. doi:10.13156/100.014.0406.

MELLO-LEITÃO C.F. 1929. Aphantochilidas e Thomisidas do Brasil. *Archivos do Museu Nacional Rio de Janeiro* 31: 9–359.

MILLOT J. 1942. Les araignées de l'Afrique Occidentale Française: Thomisidae. *Mémoires de l'Académie des Sciences de Paris* 65: 1–82.

PICKARD-CAMBRIDGE F.O. 1900. Arachnida. Araneida. 2.1n : Biologia Centrali-Americana. *Zoologia*. London: 89–192.

VAN DEN BERG A.M. 1989. An investigation into the effects of two commonly used pesticides on spider mite predator populations in cotton with special reference to spiders. MSc thesis, Rand Afrikaans University.

VAN DEN BERG M.A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., DEACON V.E. & ANDERSON S.H. 1992. Interaction between citrus psylla, *Trioza erytreae* (Hem. Triozidae), and spiders in an unsprayed citrus orchard in the Transvaal Lowveld. *Entomophaga* 37(4): 599–608.

SIMON E. 1895. Histoire naturelle des Araignées, T.1, fasc. 4. Paris, 761–1084.

WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. World Spider Catalog. Version 24. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 10 August 2023 doi: 10.24436/2.

More on the gold band jumping spider *Thyene natalii* Peckham & Peckham, 1903 in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, S. H. Foord¹ & P. Webb†²

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda Dippenaaransie@gmail.com; Stefan.Foord@univen.ac.za; ²SANSA Gauteng team member (deceased)

Abstract: The gold band jumping spider *Thyene natalii* Peckham & Peckham, 1903 has a wide distribution in Africa and is known from Ethiopia in the north to South Africa in the south. The general morphology of both sexes of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens with notes on their agrobiont behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Thyene* Simon, 1886 is represented by 52 species and subspecies of which 37 species are known from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2023). So far, 14 species have been recorded from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Most of these species have been recorded during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). One of the *Thyene* species commonly sampled was identified as *Thyene natalii* Peckham & Peckham, 1903.

Thyene natalii was described from Durban in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. This species is the only *Thyene* that has a short ovoid abdomen with an abdominal pattern composed of transverse bands. The aim of this paper is to provide more information on the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens. Their agrobiont behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa are discussed.

TAXONOMY

Thyene natalii Peckham & Peckham, 1903

Thyene strandi Caporiacco, 1939: 376 (Ethiopia).

Thyene natalii Peckham & Peckham, 1903: 227 (South Africa); Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009: 85 (Zimbabwe) (Synonym of *Thyene strandi*); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010 (South Africa).

Thyene natali Lessert, 1936: 294 (Mozambique); Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008: 216 (Zimbabwe); Dawidowicz & Wesolowska 2016: 461 (Kenya).

Description: Female body size 6–7 mm (Figs 1–2). Carapace fawn; cephalic region with layer white setae and decorated with five irregular black spots; anterior eye region with white setae; eyes circled with white scales; a cluster of black tufts of setae behind anterior posterior eyes. Abdomen ovoid; same colour as carapace; dorsally decorated with transverse bands that vary from silver to gold to brown and white iridescent scales (Figs 7–10). Legs the same colour as carapace; femur I marked, on the front face, with thin rows of dark lines, which are repeated, with less distinctness, on the femur of the second leg. Epigyne is weakly sclerotised, with small anteriorly placed depression (Figs 9–12).

Male body size 5–7 mm. (Figs 3–4): Cephalic region dark brown with a wide band of white setae around the sides and back; pale yellowish-brown band on upper sides and across the anterior thoracic part. Eye region with gold and silver iridescent scales; face marked with three lines of reddish scales that run around below the lateral eyes onto the thoracic part; rings of red setae around median eyes; tufts of black hairs behind the lateral eyes.

Figures 1–2. *Thyene natalii* female. 1. Habitus dorsal view. 2. Anterior view
Photo credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. Johan van Zyl.

Abdomen ovoid; dark with faint transverse bands of red and silvery iridescent scales. Legs: first leg robust; femora patellae and metatarsi of all legs dark, rest of legs banded. Palp brown, bulb rounded, embolus very long, encircling the bulb more than three times (Figs 5–6).

Figures 3–8. *Thyene natalii*. 3. Male habitus dorsal view. 4. Male eye pattern anterior view. 5–6. Male palp. 7–8. Epigyne. Photo credits: 3–4. Rudi Steenkamp. 5 & 7. ASD. 6 & 8. After Wesolowska & Cumming (2008).

Figures 9–12. *Thyene natalii* female showing the variation in abdominal color pattern. Photo credits: 9–11. Vida vd Walt. 12. Rudi Steenkamp.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Eswatini, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, South Africa, Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Map 1)

Eastern Cape: Addo Citrus Research Station (-33.55, 25.69); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Keurkloof district, Ferndale Farm (-33.68, 24.83); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Bathurst (-34.20, 24.7083). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein, National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); 15 km N Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

Limpopo: Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Balloon (-24.17, 30.25); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.99, 30.26); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Tshulu (-22.58, 30.81); Zanzibar Border Post (-22.57, 28.45). Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.320, 29.324). **Mpumalanga:** Burger's Hall (-25.08, 31.06); Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit district, Brondal Farm (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit district, Glenwood Farm (-29.87, 30.98); Plaston (-25.34, 31.06); Schagen (-25.43, 30.80). **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Riebeeck-West (-33.34, 18.86); Grabouw (-34.14, 19.04); Wellington (-33.65, 19.00); Knysna (-34.03, 23.03); Ruitersbos (-33.94, 22.05); Sedgefield (-34.03, 22.81).

Map 1. known distribution of *Thyene natalii* in South Africa

LIFESTYLE

In South Africa *T. natalii* was collected from foliage of shrubs and trees from all the floral biomes except in the more arid biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). They make retreats with silk threads between leaves. The species was also sampled on the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* (fever trees) in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad, 2016).

It was collected from several agroecosystems such as avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005), citrus and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001a, b), and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) and is identified as one of South Africa's agrobiont species.

In macadamia orchards, spiders were collected over a 12-month period (July 1997–June 1998) from three orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa using dichlorvos as a knock-down spray (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001a).

Figure 13. Seasonal fluctuation of *Thyene natalii* in three macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld, South Africa (After Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001a).

Of the 2778 spiders collected, 73% belonged to the Salticidae, represented by 17 species with *T. natalii* (394 specimens) the second most abundant species representing 30% of all the spiders collected from macadamia. It was recorded throughout the year from the three orchards in Mpumalanga (Fig. 13). The numbers peaked in February, April, and September. Of the specimens recorded females represent 41%, males 37% and juveniles 22% (Fig. 14) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2001b).

In two avocado orchards in Mpumalanga, of all the spiders collected over a year period, two *Thyene* species *T. natalii* and *T. coccineovittata* represented 22.5% of the total number of spiders sampled. A total of 405 *T. natalii* specimens were sampled, representing 11 % of all spiders sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005).

AGGRESSIVE MIMICRY

While sorting the spiders sampled from different Macadamia orchards, we came across a few dead Mediterranean fruit flies *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Figs 14–15). The fly, commonly also known as medflies, is native to sub-Saharan Africa and it has no near relatives in the Western Hemisphere. It is one of the most destructive fruit pests in the world.

T. natalii (Figs 16–17) resembled the medflies closely. They both have dark spots on the cephalothorax and similar horizontal bands on the abdomen. Even the lines on the front legs of the spider resemble the lines on the wings of the fly. This might be aggressive mimicry that suggests *T. natalii* prey on the fruit flies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The following photographers are thanked for sharing their photographs: John Richter, Rudi Steenkamp, Vida vd Walt, and Johan van Zyl.

Figures 14–15. Dorsal view of adult male Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann). Photo credits Katja (iNaturalist).

Figures 16–18. Adult female *Thyene natalii*. 16–17. Dorsal view. 18. Anterior view. Photo credits 16–17. Peter Webb. 18. Vida vd Walt.

REFERENCES

CAPORIACCO L. DI 1939. Arachnida. In: Missione biologica nel paese dei Borana. Raccolte zoologiche. *Reale Accademia d'Italia, Roma* 3: 303–385.

DAWIDOWICZ A. & WESOŁOWSKA W. 2016. Jumping spiders (Araneae: Salticidae) of Kenya collected by Åke Holm. *Annales Zoologici, Warszawa* 66(3): 437–466.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 29-38. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831547>.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: A review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG M.A. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2001a. Spiders in macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa: species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 7: 39–46.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG M.A. & VAN DEN BERG A.M. 2001b. Salticid spiders in macadamia orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae: Salticidae). *African Plant Protection* 7: 47–51.

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., VAN DEN BERG A., VAN DEN BERG M.A. & FOORD S.H. 2005. Spiders in avocado orchards in the Mpumalanga Lowveld of South Africa: Species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 11: 8–16.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN ZYL J. 2023. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Spider diversity of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Gauteng province, South Africa. *SANSa Newsletter* 44: 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7539738>.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2020. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Addo Elephant National Park in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 62(1), a1578. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v62i1.1578>.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. JOCQUÉ R., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R. & WEBB P. 2016. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders Arachnida Araneae of the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Limpopo Province South Africa. *Koedoe* 58(1) 8 pages a1405. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v58i1.1405>.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., SCHOEMAN C., HAHN N. & LYLE R. 2019. Spider checklist for the Blouberg, in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, South Africa. *Bothalia* 49(1), a2455. <https://doi.org/10.4102/abc.v49i1.2455>.
- FOORD S.H., MAFADZA M.M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN RENSBURG B.J. 2008. Small scale heterogeneity in spider (Arachnida: Araneae) species composition and assemblage structure in the Soutpansberg, South Africa. *African Zoology* 43: 156–174.
- HADDAD C.R. 2016. Diversity and ecology of spider assemblages associated with *Vachellia xanthophloea* bark in a South African reserve Arachnida: Araneae. *African Entomology* 24(2): 321–333.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2015. DIVERSITY OF NON-ACARINE ARACHNIDS OF THE OPHATHE GAME RESERVE SOUTH AFRICA: TESTING A RAPID SAMPLING PROTOCOL. *KOEDOE* 57(1) ART. #1255 15 PAGES. [HTTP://DX.DOI.ORG/10.4102/KOEDOE.V57I1.1255](http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/KOEDOE.V57I1.1255).
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L. & LYLE R. 2013. THE FAUNISTIC DIVERSITY OF SPIDERS ARACHNIDA ARANEAE OF THE GRASSLAND BIOME IN SOUTH AFRICA. *TRANSACTIONS OF THE ROYAL SOCIETY OF SOUTH AFRICA* 68: 97–122.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WESOŁOWSKA W. 2006. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the Ndumo Game Reserve, Maputaland, South Africa. *Koedoe* 49: 1–22.
- HADDAD C.R., HONIBALL A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & SLOTOU R. 2009. Spiders as potential indicators of elephant-induced habitat changes in endemic sand forest Maputaland South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 48: 446–460.
- LESSERT R. DE 1936. Araignées de l'Afrique orientale portugaise, recueillies par MM. P. Lesne et B.-B. Cott. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 43: 207–306.
- PECKHAM G.W. & PECKHAM E.G. 1903. New species of the family Attidae from South Africa, with notes on the distribution of the genera found in the Ethiopian region. *Transactions of the Wisconsin Academy of Sciences, Arts and Letters* 14(1): 173–278.
- PRÓSZYŃSKI J. 2017. Pragmatic classification of the world's Salticidae (Araneae). *Ecologica Montenegrina* 12: 1–133. [doi:10.37828/em.2017.12.1](https://doi.org/10.37828/em.2017.12.1).
- WESOŁOWSKA W. & CUMMING M.S. 2008. Taxonomy and natural history of a species rich assemblage of jumping spiders (Araneae: Salticidae); a long-term study of a suburban site in Zimbabwe. *Annales Zoologici, Warszawa* 58: 167–230.
- WESOŁOWSKA W. & HADDAD C.R. 2009. Jumping spiders (Araneae: Salticidae) of the Ndumo Game Reserve, Maputaland, South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 50: 13–103. [doi:10.5733/afin.050.0102](https://doi.org/10.5733/afin.050.0102).
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. World Spider Catalog. Version 24. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on May 2023 [doi: 10.24436/2](https://doi.org/10.24436/2).

More on the black-tail sheet-web spider *Ostearius melanopygius* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879) in South Africa (Araneae: Linyphiidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, C.R. Haddad² & R. Steenkamp³

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda; ²Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State;

³SANSA Free State team member and Spider Club of Southern Africa

Abstract: The cosmopolitan black-tail sheet-web Spider *Ostearius melanopygius* was for the first time reported from South Africa in 1984. The species was possibly accidentally introduced to South Africa but is now well established in South Africa where it is found in all nine provinces. Photographs of live specimens are provided with notes on their distribution and conservation status in South Africa as well as agrobiont status.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Ostearius* Hull, 1911 is represented by only two species *Ostearius melanopygius* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1879), a cosmopolitan species described from New Zealand, and *O. muticus* Gao, Gao & Zhu, 1994 from China (World Spider Catalog, 2023). *Ostearius melanopygius* in the course of time appeared to have a world-wide distribution from some countries in Africa, Europe, Asia, and South America.

Ostearius melanopygius was for the first time reported from a few localities in South Africa by Jocqué (1984). The species has been introduced maybe with imported plant material but is now well established in South Africa where it was recorded from all nine provinces (Fig. 15). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the country and the species was frequently sampled especially in crops. The aim of this paper is to provide more information on the morphology of both sexes based on live specimens, their behaviour, distribution, conservation, and agrobiont status in South Africa.

TAXONOMY

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female and male 3–4 mm. Carapace dark, shiny (Figs 1–3) with faint striae (Fig. 7); eyes in two rows; large and rather closely grouped, with the anterior eyes in a straight and the posterior eyes in a slightly recurved line (Fig. 7); posterior eyes are less than one diameter apart; sternum heart shape, brown (Fig. 6); chelicerae straight and similar in both sexes; with a fang groove with five promarginal teeth; clypeus is lower than the median ocular quadrangle and hardly protruding (Figs 7, 9). Abdomen longer than wide; orange red and shiny with small black area posterior around spinnerets (Figs 5–6, 13). Legs are yellow brown, rather long and slender. Male is slightly smaller than female. Male palp distinguished by the bifid form of the retrolateral tibial apophysis (Fig. 11) and the long, gently curved, rigid embolus (Fig. 12). Female epigyne (Fig. 10).

Figures 9–12. *Ostearius melanopygius*. 9. Female carapace. 10. Epigyne. 11. Tibial apophysis. 12. Male palp. Credit: From Bosmans (2007).

Figures 1–8. The Black-tail sheet-web spider *Ostearius melanopygius*. 2–4. Male. 1, 5–8. Female. Photo credits: Rudi Steenkamp.

Figure 13. *Ostearius melanopygius* female in web in Bloemfontein. Photo credit: Nicolette Josling.

LIFESTYLE

The species makes sheet-webs usually close to the soil surface in a variety of habitats. It is an introduced species, but it seems quite established in South Africa where it was found in all nine provinces (Fig. 15). They were sampled from all the floral biomes in South Africa except the Succulent Karoo Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). They are known as frequent aeronauts that balloon in order to disperse. It was also recorded from a cave in North West province (Jocqué, 1984; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Myburg, 2009).

In South Africa they were frequently sampled from pitfall traps in agroecosystems and might have been imported with plant material. Nineteen linyphiid species have been sampled from crops and orchards in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013) such as apple, citrus, and pistachio orchards (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006) and crops like cabbage, cotton (Mellett *et al.*, 2006), maize, strawberries, tomatoes, and vineyards. Two of the 19 linyphiid species were recognised as agrobionts, namely the cosmopolitan species *O. melanopygius*, which was abundant on cotton, maize, and pistachio, and *Eperigone fradeorum*, which was abundant in cotton fields. In South African maize, the most abundant linyphiids were *O. melanopygius*, *Agyneta habra*, and *Limoneta sirimoni* (Dippenaar-Schoeman, unpublished report, 1989). In pistachio orchards in the Northern Cape, *O. melanopygius* dominated the ground-dwelling fauna and was dominant in all the orchards sampled, comprising 30% of pitfall specimens and 26% of hand-collected specimens and can be considered a pistachio agrobiont (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006). Adults of both sexes are found throughout the year (Fig. 15).

Figure 14. Numbers and phenology of *Ostearius melanopygius* collected by pitfall trapping in pistachio orchards in the Prieska district, Northern Cape province, from August 2001 to July 2002 (pooled data of three orchards). Grey bars indicate immatures, white bars males, and black bars females. (from Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South America. Introduced to Canada, Europe, Canary Is. to Egypt and Turkey, South Africa, China, Malaysia, Indonesia, and New Zealand (World Spider Catalog, 2023). New: Namibia (Griffin & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1992); Tanzania (Russell-Smith, 2020); Kenya (Kioko *et al.*, 2021).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 15)

Eastern Cape: Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91) [Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023]; Peddie (Gibraltar Rock) (-33.19, 27.12). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Parys (Waterval) (-26.9, 27.45); Viljoenskroon (-27.21, 26.96); Vrede (-27.43; 29.13). **Gauteng:** Abe Bailey Nature Reserve (-26.36, 27.4); Cullinan (Renosterkop) (-25.66, 28.51); Olifantsfontein (-25.96, 28.24); Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23) [Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991]; Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46), Lodge (-24.53, 28.50). **Mpumalanga:** Bethal (Farm Maleas Estate) (-26.44, 29.46); Delmas (Farm Rietvallei) (26.08, 28.57); Groblersdal Agricultural Research Station (-25.16, 29.39); Loskop Research Station (-25.17, 29.4); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Nelspruit Agricultural College (-25.47, 30.96); Oudestad Research Station (-25.16, 29.39); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Potchefstroom ARC Experimental Farm (-26.7, 27.09); Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (Farm 394) (-32.96, 23.67); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Elsenburg (-33.85, 18.83); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Hermanus (Fisherhaven) (-34.47, 19.27); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Swellendam (-34.02, 20.42); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

Figure 15: Map showing the known distribution of *Ostearius melanopygius* in South Africa.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has been sampled from six protected areas in South Africa such as: Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2013, Haddad *et al.*, 2015); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009) and Rust de Winter (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). There is no known threats to the species and is listed as Least Concern.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank Nicolette Josling for sharing the photograph (Fig. 13).

REFERENCES

- BERLAND L. 1932. Voyage de MM. L. Chopard et A Mequignon aux Acorcs. Araignees. *Annales de la Societe entomologique de France* 101: 69–84.
- BOSMANS R. 2007. Contribution to the knowledge of the Linyphiidae of the Maghreb. Part XII. Miscellaneous erigonine genera and additional records (Araneae: Linyphiidae: Erigoninae). *Bulletin & Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 143: 117–163.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., HADDAD C.R. & LE ROUX E. 2021. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Bontebok National Park in the Western Cape Province, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 38: 13–21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5947479>.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & MYBURGH J.G. 2009. A review of the cave spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 64(1): 53–61.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: A review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. Spiders in South African cotton fields: Species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 5: 93–103.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOURIE R., HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & GROBLER A. 2013. Ecology of the plant-dwelling spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 55(1), 9 pages. doi: 10.4102/koedoe.v55i1.1113.
- GRIFFIN E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1992. A checklist of and references to the Namibian spider fauna (Arachnida, Araneae). *Cimbebasia* 13: 155–181.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2005. Epigeic spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in Nama Karoo grassland in the Northern Cape Province. *Navorsing nasionale Museum, Bloemfontein* 21(1): 1–10.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2006. Epigeic spiders (Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 12–22.
- HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2009. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the De Hoop Nature Reserve, Western Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 51(1): 1–9.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* doi:10.1080/0035919X.2013.773267.
- HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & PEKÁR S. 2005. Arboreal spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 11: 32–41.
- HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.R., FOURIE R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2015. Effects of a fast-burning spring fire on the ground-dwelling spider assemblages (Arachnida: Araneae) in a central South African grassland habitat. *African Zoology* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15627020.2015.1088400>.
- HADDAD C.R., LOUW S. VD M. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2004. Spiders (Araneae) in ground covers of pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 10(2): 97–107.
- JOCQUÉ R. 1984. Linyphiidae (Araneae) from South Africa. Part I: The collection of the Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria. *Journal of the Entomological Society of South Africa* 47: 121–146.
- KIOKO G.M., MARUSIK Y.M., LI S.Q., KIOKO E.N. & JI L.Q. 2021. Checklist of the spiders (Araneae) of Kenya. *African Invertebrates* 62(1): 49–229 doi:10.3897/AfrInvertebr.62.58776.
- MELLET M.A., SCHOEMAN A.S. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2006. Effect of Bt-cotton cultivation on spider (Arachnida: Araneae) populations near Marble Hall, Mpumalanga, South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 40–50.
- RUSSELL-SMITH A. 2020. A checklist of the spiders of Tanzania. *Journal of East African Natural History* 109(1): 1–41.
- VAN DEN BERG A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1991. Ground living spiders from an area where the harvester termite *Hodotermes mossambicus* occurs in South Africa. *Phytophylactica* 23: 247–253.
- WHITEMORE C., SLOTOV S., CROUCH T.E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2001. Checklist of spiders (Araneae) from a savanna ecosystem, Northern Province, South Africa: including a new family record. *Durban Museum Novitates* 26: 10–19.
- WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831510>.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. Version 24.5. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on August 2023. doi: 10.24436/2.

More on the black-palp wolf spider *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell, 1903 in South Africa (Araneae: Lycosidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & P. Webb^{‡2}

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda; dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSA Gauteng team member (deceased)

Abstract: The black-palp wolf spider *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell, 1903 has a wide distribution in Southern Africa and is known from Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa. The species is commonly found in agroecosystems and is recognised as one of five agrobiont species in South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed, with photographs of live specimens and notes on their behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa.

Key words: agroecosystems, agrobiont, behaviour, conservation, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Pardosa* C.L. Koch, 1847 is represented by 528 species and subspecies, with 10 species recorded from South Africa. In this paper we provide more information on *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell, 1903 a Southern African endemic described by Purcell (1903) from Montagu in the Western Cape. The species occurs wide throughout Southern Africa but is suspected to have a wider distribution in Africa. In South Africa, it is known from all nine provinces.

The aim of this paper is to collate all information on the species. This includes behaviour, biology, distribution, and conservation status in South Africa, with notes on their agrobiont status. The data were gathered during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

TAXONOMY

Pardosa crassipalpis Purcell, 1903

Pardosa crassipalpis Purcell, 1903: 138; Roewer, 1959: 122; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1977: 26; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 19.

Diagnostic characteristics: Female (4–5 mm). Carapace with dark lateral bands, the median yellow band broad, dilated in eye region; submarginal yellowish bands with a row of black spots laterally, the margin itself marked with a series of black bands (Figs 1, 3, 4). Anterior row of eyes straight or slightly procurved, the posterior median eyes are slightly larger than the laterals (Fig. 9). Sternum pale yellowish. Abdomen dark at the sides above (Figs 3–4), the median band more or less fused to form a single broad yellow area extending to spinnerets; with lateral bands decorated with black spots (in alcohol), white in live.

Legs pale yellowish, spotted, and banded with black, except tarsi; inferior spines on tibia, and metatarsus of first leg long. Epigyne longer than wide, somewhat triangular, with wavy margins and narrowed anteriorly (Figs 5–7).

Male (4–4.5 mm). Resembling the female in colour, except the distal segments of the legs are not banded and the first femur is more thickened at base in front. Palp distinct large covered with black setae (Figs 2 & 10).

LIFESTYLE

Pardosa crassipalpis is one of the smaller lycosids and, like the others, is a very quick-moving and agile ground spider. They can tolerate a wide range of habitats or ecological conditions (eurotopic), and they are found in all the floral biomes except the more arid ones (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). They are present throughout the year and have a wide distribution throughout South Africa (Fig. 11).

The life cycle and some ecological aspects of the spider *P. crassipalpis* were studied (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1977). It is a univoltine species and the males pass through seven instars before reaching maturity and the females through eight. The egg sac is carried by the female (Figs 1 & 9) and during the reproductive phase the female spider produces an average of three egg sacs, with an average number of 23.3 eggs per sac. The construction of the egg sac took place at night and the new egg sac is bluish grey and later turns yellowish white. The complete egg sac is lenticular and is attached to the spinnerets of the female.

Figures 1–2. *Pardosa crassipalpis*. 1. Female with egg sac. 2. Male showing the thick black palps, hence the common name. Photo credits: 1. Peter Webb. 2. Vida vd Walt.

Figures 3–7. *Pardosa crassipalpis*. 3–4 Female dorsal view. 5–7. Epigynum. Photo credits: 3 & 5. Charles Haddad. 4 & 7. From Roewer (1959).

Twenty-three species of lycosids have been sampled in crops in South Africa but *P. crassipalpis* was the most abundant and sampled from crops such as cabbage, cotton, lucerne, maize, potatoes, sorghum, strawberries, sugar cane, sunflower, and tomatoes. They were also abundant in commercial pine plantations, and in apple, citrus, pistachio, pear, and pecans orchards. Therefore, the species is recognised as one of the agrobiont species in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

In surveys in strawberry fields at the ARC Roodeplaat campus, *P. crassipalpis* was the dominant species present, representing 82% of all the lycosids sampled and 63% of all the spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976, 1979). They were observed on the leaves and flowers of plants or running on the ground and hiding under the plants.

In cotton they were also the numerically dominant species and was recorded from five cotton-growing areas. They prey on red spider mites (*Tetranychus* spp.) and various stages of cotton bollworm larvae (*Helicoverpa armigera*) in the laboratory (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). They are also the dominant family at the ground level in Bt cotton fields, representing 62.5% of all the spiders collected (Mellet *et al.*, 2006).

In pistachio orchards in the Northern Cape the 262 *P. crassipalpis* collected contributed 15.5% of all the spiders sampled. In Fig. 8 the number and phenology of *P. crassipalpis* collected by pitfall trapping in pistachio orchards in the Prieska district, Northern Cape province, are shown. They were present throughout the year, with adults peaking in October to January.

Figure 8. Numbers and phenology of *Pardosa crassipalpis* collected by pitfall trapping in pistachio orchards in the Prieska district, Northern Cape province, from August 2001 to July 2002 (pooled data of three orchards). Grey bars indicate immatures, white bars males, and black bars females. (from Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006).

Figures 9–10. *Pardosa crassipalpis*. 9. Female with egg sac. 10. Male. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Coates (1974), Dippenaar-Schoeman (1976), and Botha (1986) found *P. crassipalpis* to be active predators of red spider mites (*Tetranychus cinnabarinus*) in various crops in South Africa. In the USA, Whitcomb *et al.* (1963) found that lycosids swarm over cotton plants at night in summer and that *Pardosa* spp. prey on pink bollworm moths. They presumably destroy first and second-instar larvae of the bollworm on the plant, as well as those that fall to the ground. Bollworm moths are also vulnerable to predation during their brief exposure on the soil surface following emergence from their pupae (Whitcomb, 1967).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Namibia, Botswana, South Africa, and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

The known distribution of *P. crassipalpis* is shown in Fig. 11. Purcell (1903) described *P. crassipalpis* from specimens collected at the Hot Baths near Montagu. It is presently reported from all nine provinces. For detail locality records, see Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2021).

Figure 11. Known distribution of *Pardosa crassipalpis* in South Africa.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has been sampled from six protected areas in South Africa. There are no known threats to the species and it is listed as Least Concern.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Charles Haddad for sharing the photographs (Figs 3 & 5) and Vida vd Walt for Fig. 2.

REFERENCES

BOTHA J.H. 1986. An evaluation of the influence of some pesticides on natural enemies of spider mite populations in cotton. Unpublished PhD thesis, Rand Afrikaans University. 276 pp.

COATES T.J.D. 1974. The influence of some natural enemies and pesticides on various populations of *Tetranychus cinnabarinus* (Boisduval), *T. lombardii* Baker & Pritchard and *T. ludeni* Zacher (Acari: Tetranychidae) with aspects of their biologies. *Entomology Memoir, Department of Agricultural Technical Services, Republic of South Africa*, vol. 42, 40 pp.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1976. An ecological study of the spider population in strawberries with special reference to the role of *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell (Araneae: Lycosidae) in the control of *Tetranychus cinnabarinus* (Boisduval). MSc thesis, Rand Afrikaans University. 119 pp.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1977. The biology of *Pardosa crassipalpis* Purcell (Araneae: Lycosidae). *Journal of the Entomological Society of Southern Africa* 40: 225–236.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1979. Spider communities in strawberry beds: Seasonal changes in numbers and species composition. *Phytomyllactica* 11: 1–4.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L. N. 2021. *The Lycosidae of South Africa*. Version 1: part 2 (L-Z). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 82 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6324723.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R. LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): A review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70(3): 245–275.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M., HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: A review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DEN BERG A.M. & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. Spiders in South African cotton fields: Species diversity and abundance (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Plant Protection* 5: 93–103.

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.

HADDAD C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2006. Epigeic spiders (Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 12–22.

HADDAD C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L. & LYLE R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68 (2): 97–122.

MELLET M.A., SCHOEMAN A.S. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2006. The effect of Bt-cotton cultivation on spider (Arachnida: Araneae) populations in Marble Hall, South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 40–50.

PURCELL W.F. 1903. New South African spiders of the families Migidae, Ctenizidae, Barychelidae, Dipluridae and Lycosidae. *Annals of the South African Museum* 3: 69–42.

ROEWER C.F. 1959. Araneae Lycosaeformia II Lycosidae). *Exploration du Parc National de l'Upemba, Mission G. F. de Witte* 55: 1–518.

VAN DEN BERG A.M. 1989. An investigation into the effects of two commonly used pesticides on spider mite predator populations in cotton with special reference to spiders. Unpublished MSc thesis, Rand Afrikaans University. 121 pp.

WHITCOMB W.H. 1967. Field studies on predators of the second-instar bollworm *Heliothis zea* (Boddie) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *Journal of the Georgia Entomological Society* 2: 113–118.

Gauteng urban area surveys 2. Checklist of the spiders of the Groenkloof Nature Reserve in Pretoria, South Africa (Arachnida, Araneae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, R. Lyle² & P. Webb†³

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda; ²ARC – Plant Health and Protection, Private Bag X134, Queenswood 0121, South Africa;

³SANSA team member (deceased)

ABSTRACT: Little is known about the diversity of spiders in urban areas in South Africa. This survey of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) forms part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of SANSa. The results of sampling undertaken in the Groenkloof Nature Reserve in the Gauteng province, South Africa, are provided. A total of 112 species, 84 genera, from 35 families were recorded. Sampling was mainly done by sweeping and hand collecting. The most species-rich families were the Salticidae (20 spp.), Gnaphosidae (12 spp.), followed by the Lycosidae (11 spp.), while 16 families are represented by singletons. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species. Two of the species are Vulnerable and two are Endangered.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, diversity, South African National Survey of Arachnida, urban surveys

INTRODUCTION

It is estimated that 16.8% of the South African human population resides in Gauteng, and the province has the highest population density and the highest urbanisation levels. Consequently, the biodiversity in the province is highly threatened by industrialisation, mining, agriculture, and especially urbanisation. There are current high demands for the provision of land and basic services to alleviate poor living conditions. Therefore, the successful conservation of biodiversity within Gauteng requires the identification of priority areas where development and habitat transformation should be discouraged, and conservation efforts should be put in place.

Interest in the invertebrate faunas of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last 20 years. These areas are not just seen as human-modified habitats of low intrinsic biodiversity, but as potential corridors for dispersal of wildlife through urban areas, both within and outside towns and cities. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), few papers on spider diversity in urban and suburban areas have been published in the last few years (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). In the Free State, several studies have been undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden, Bloemfontein (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2019; Neethling & Haddad, 2013), while in the Eastern Cape a checklist of the spiders of Jeffreys Bay was provided (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023). In Gauteng, surveys were undertaken in several reserves in Pretoria (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014) as part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of SANSa. The first paper dealt with the diversity of the Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022).

Groenkloof Nature Reserve was the first game sanctuary in Africa proclaimed by President Paul Kruger in 1895. Its main purpose was to protect the Oribi and other game that were being wiped out by hunters. After 1910, part of the area was rented out for the establishment of commercial plantations for the delivery of wood and the production of paper. By the late 1950s, the City Council of Pretoria became the owner of the area. When the reserve was proclaimed in 1994, the plantations were removed to allow the natural vegetation to regenerate and since 1999 the reserve was stocked with various game species.

This paper presents the first species list on the spider fauna of the Groenkloof Nature Reserve. Information on endemism and conservation status for each of the 112 species is provided.

Figures 1–3. In the Groenkloof Nature Reserve the highveld and bushveld regions meet on low, broken ridges varying in steepness. Photos: 2 & 3. Peter Webb.

Fig. 4. Survey area Groenkloof Nature Reserve, Gauteng.

METHOD

Study area: Groenkloof Nature Reserve (25°47'S, 28°12'E) (GNR) is located adjacent to the Fountains Valley at the southern entrance to Pretoria. The reserve of 600 ha is managed by the Department of Nature Conservation. GNR is only 5 km from the Pretoria city centre and borders the Fountains Valley in its northern part.

Vegetation: GNR is situated where the highveld and bushveld regions meet and features low, broken ridges varying in steepness. Open grassland occurs along the Apies Valley and the higher plateau. The vegetation is semipen thicket, dominated by a variety of woody species, including *Senegalia caffra*, *Searsia leptodictya*, *Combretum mole*, and *Dombeya rotundifolia*. The under-story is dominated by a variety of grasses. A mature woodland of white stinkwood trees is also present on the reserve.

Sampling methods and identification: The second author (RL) and third author (PW) sampled spiders over a period of 10 years. Live spiders were sampled, photographed, and then preserved in 70% ethanol by PW. Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (ASD). Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because they were immature or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved.

Endemicity value: The endemicity value for each species is provided (Table 3) based on its currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised: 6 = when GNR is the type locality; 5 = GE, endemic to the Gauteng province but wider than the type locality; 4 = SAE endemic to South Africa but known from two adjoining provinces; 3 = SAE South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining; 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic); 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider (C).

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of all South African species is now available. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DD (Data Deficient). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE) and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Groenkloof Nature Reserve with the total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.).

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Philodromidae	2	2
Ammoxenidae	1	1	Pholcidae	1	1
Araneidae	4	4	Phyxelididae	1	1
Atypidae	1	1	Pisauridae	3	3
Bemmeridae	1	1	Prodidomidae	2	2
Caponiidae	1	1	Salticidae	10	20
Cheiracanthiidae	2	2	Scytodidae	1	2
Clubionidae	1	1	Sparassidae	1	1
Corinnidae	1	1	Sicariidae	1	2
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	2	2
Eresidae	2	2	Theridiidae	4	4
Gnaphosidae	9	12	Thomisidae	6	8
Idiopidae	4	6	Trachelidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	2	2	Uloboridae	2	2
Lycosidae	6	11	Zodariidae	4	4
Oxyopidae	2	6		84	112

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Groenkloof Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION STATUS	CODE	NO SPP.	%
Data deficient	DD	3	2.8
Not evaluated	NE	3	2.8
Least concern	LC	103	91.8
Vulnerable	V	2	1.8
Endangered	EN	2	1.8
ENDEMICITY			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	LC	8	7.1
1 – African endemics (AE)	LC	42	37.5
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	LC	29	25.9
3 – SA endemics (SAE):	LC	25	22.3
4 – SA (SAE): 2 adjacent provinces		3	2.8
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)		3	2.7
6 – Type locality		0	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 112 species, 84 genera, from 35 families were recorded (Tables 1 & 3). Two species of the Oxyopidae and Zodariidae could not be identified to species level as their taxonomy was still unresolved. As part of the SMC project of SANSa, the first survey dealt with the diversity of the Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022), where 103 species from 31 families were recorded. When comparing the two surveys, it was found that 42 species from 21 families were recorded from both reserves.

Family diversity: Of the 35 spider families collected from GNR (Tables 1 & 2), the most species-rich families were the Salticidae (20 spp.), Gnaphosidae (12 spp.), followed by the Lycosidae (11 spp.), while 16 families are represented by singletons.

Endemicity: Eight species (7.1%) sampled at GNR have a wide distribution wider than Africa, while 37.5% are African endemics (AE) and 25.9% are Southern African endemics and 27.8% are South African endemics.

Three species are Gauteng endemics, two Idiopidae species *Galeosoma hirsutum* Hewitt, 1916 and *G. pallidum* Hewitt, 1916 and a Sicariidae species *Loxosceles speluncarum* Simon, 1893. Three species are near endemics: *Calommata transvaalica* Hewitt, 1916 of the Atypidae and *Idiops gunningi* Hewitt, 1913 of the Idiopidae are also recorded from Limpopo and *Loxosceles parramae* Newlands, 1981 (Sicariidae) is also recorded from the Free State.

Species of special concern: The following four species are of special concern.

1. *Calommata transvaalica* —Vulnerable

Figures 5–8. *Calommata transvaalica*. 5–6. Male. 7–8. Female. Photo credits: 5 & 7. Charles Haddad. 6. Ian Engelbrecht. 7. Charles Haddad. 8. M. Benic.

Calommata transvaalica is a South African endemic described in 1916 from Roodeplaat, South Africa. It is known only from the Gauteng and Limpopo provinces (Soutpansberg and Blouberg). Parts of its habitat have been threatened in Gauteng due to crop cultivation and urban development, and the species is suspected to occur at fewer than 10 locations. It is therefore listed as Vulnerable under the B criterion (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

2. *Loxosceles speluncarum* —Vulnerable

Figures 9–10. *Loxosceles speluncarum* female. Photo credits: Jarrod Todd.

Loxosceles speluncarum is known only from three cave complexes in the Fountain area in Pretoria. It is a troglobite cave species that are more abundant in totally dark areas where they have been

recorded from crevices or wandering around on the cave walls. This species is potentially threatened by disturbance of its specialist cave habitat, and is therefore listed as Vulnerable under criterion D2 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021a).

3. *Galeosoma hirsutum* —Endangered

Figures 11–12. *Galeosoma hirsutum*. 11. Female 12. Abdomen. Photo credits: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Galeosoma hirsutum is a Gauteng endemic described by Hewitt (1916) from Roodeplaat. This species is known from fewer than five extant locations and is threatened throughout its range by urban development. It therefore qualifies for listing as Endangered under criterion B (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021b).

4. *Galeosoma pallidum* —Endangered

Figures 13–14. *Galeosoma pallidum*. 13. Female. 14. Abdomen. Photo credits: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Galeosoma pallidum is a Gauteng endemic described by Hewitt (1916) from Saltpan. The species is recorded from a few localities, with six recorded prior to 1915. Currently extant at fewer than five locations and threatened throughout its range by urban development. This species qualifies for listing as Endangered under criterion B (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021b).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Prof. Charles Haddad of the University of the Free State for the identification of the families Corinnidae, Salticidae, and Trachelidae and the following photographers for the use of his photographs: Charles Haddad, Ian Engelbrecht, Jarrod Todd, and M. Benic.

REFERENCES

- BUTLER V.P. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. Spider assemblages associated with leaf litter of three tree species in central South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Journal of Ecology* 49: 301–310.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020. *he Atypidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 7 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6032638.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2021a. *The Sicariidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 24 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7162164.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., & LOTZ L.N. 2021b. *The Idiopidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene 62 pp. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6324502.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LYLE R. 2014. Several SANSA projects underway – Three new projects in Gauteng. *SANSA Newsletter* 20: 10.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2022. Gauteng Urban Surveys 1. Checklist of the spiders of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve in Pretoria, South Africa (Arachnida, Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 41: 26–34. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6482651
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., SETHUSA T. & RAIMONDO D. 2020. The South African National Red List of spiders: Patterns, threats, and conservation. *Journal of Arachnology* 48: 110–118.
- FOURIE R., HADDAD C.R. & JOCQUÉ R. 2011. A revision of the purse-web spider genus *Calommata* Lucas, 1837 (Araneae, Atypidae) in the Afrotropical region. *ZooKeys* 95: 1–28.
- HADDAD C.R., LINDE J.C., DE JAGER C. & FOORD S.H. 2019. Habitats and cardinal directions are key variables structuring spider leaf litter assemblages under *Searsia lancea*. *Pedobiologia – Journal of Soil Ecology* 73: 10–19.
- HEWITT J. 1916. Descriptions of new South African spiders. *Annals of the Transvaal Museum* 5: 180–213.
- NEETHLING J.A. & HADDAD C.R. 2013. Arboreal spider assemblages associated with four tree species in the Grassland Biome of central South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 123–131.
- TUCKER R.W.E. 1920. Spiders of Kirstenbosch. *Journal of the Botanical Society of South Africa* 6: 21–24.
- WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 45: 19–28. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831510.

Figures 15–30. Species from Groenkloof Nature Reserve. 15. *Benoitia ocellata* (Agelenidae). 16. *Neoscona hirta* (Araneidae). 17. *Cyrtophora citricola* (Araneidae). 18. *Cyphalonotus larvatus* (Araneidae). 19. *Caponia spiralifera* (Caponiidae). 20. *Cheiracanthium* sp. (Cheiracanthiidae). 21. *Clubiona bevisi* (Clubionidae). 22. *Trephopoda parvipalpa* (Gnaphosidae). 23. *Hogna transvaalica* (Lycosidae). Oxyopidae: 24. *Oxyopes bothai*. 25. *Oxyopes affinis*. 26. *Oxyopes longispinosus*. 27. *Oxyopes jacksoni*. 28. *Vidole sothoana* (Phyxelididae). 29. *Afropisaura rothiformis* (Pisauridae). 30. *Eleleis limpopo* (Prodidomidae). Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 31–44. Species from Groenkloof Nature Reserve. Salticidae: 31. *Evarcha flagellaris*. 32. *Afraflacilla elegans*. 33. *Heliophanus nanus*. 34. *Thyene thynioides*. 35. *Anyphops barbertonensis* (Selenopidae). 36. *Loxosceles parramae* (Sicariidae). Theridiidae: 37. *Tidarren cuneolatum*. 38. *Steatoda capensis*. Thomisidae: 39. *Diaea viridipes*. 40. *Runcinia flavida*. 41. *Synema imitatrix*. Uloboridae: 42. *Uloborus plumipes*. 43. *Miagrammopes brevicaudus*. Zodariidae: 44. *Systenoplacis vandami*. 45. *Capheris schoemanae*. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Groenkloof Nature Reserve (GNR) listing their endemismy (END), conservation status (CON), and country endemismy (CEND).

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
AGELENIDAE	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900) (Fig. 15)	1	LC	AE
AMAUROBIIDAE	<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
ARANEIDAE	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881) (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775) (Fig. 17)	0	LC	C
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844) (Fig. 16)	1	LC	AE
ATYPIDAE	<i>Calommata transvaalica</i> Hewitt, 1916	4	VU	SAE
BEMMERIDAE	<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC	SAE
CAPONIIDAE	<i>Caponia spiralifera</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 19)	3	LC	SAE
CHEIRACANTHIDAE	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona floribadensis</i> Lotz, 2003 (Fig. 20)	3	LC	SAE
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923 (Fig. 21)	2	LC	STHE
CORINNIDAE	<i>Messapus martini</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
CTENIDAE	<i>Ctenus transvaalensis</i> Benoit, 1981	3	LC	SAE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE	
ERESIDAE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Amoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
	<i>Trephopoda parvipalpa</i> (Tucker, 1923) (Fig. 22)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
IDIOPIDAE	<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Galeosoma hirsutum</i> Hewitt, 1916	5	EN	SAE
	<i>Galeosoma pallidum</i> Hewitt, 1915	5	EN	SAE
	<i>Galeosoma planiscutatum</i> Hewitt, 1919	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Idiops gunningi</i> Hewitt, 1913	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Allocosa gracilitarsis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898) (Fig. 23)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa manubriata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
OXYOPIDAE	<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 24)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915 (Fig. 27)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938 (Fig. 26)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Oxyopes morpho</i> sp. 3		NE	
	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
PHOLCIDAE	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
PHYXELIDIDAE	<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990 (Fig. 28)	2	LC	STHE
PISAURIDAE	<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908) (Fig. 29)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euprosthopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
PRODIDOMIDAE	<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Eleleis limpopo</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020 (Fig. 30)	1	LC	AE
SALTICIDAE	<i>Afraflacilla elegans</i> (Wesołowska & Cumming, 2008) (Fig. 32)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesołowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesołowska & Cumming, 2008 (Fig. 31)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus infaustus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesołowska, 2003 (Fig. 33)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus orchestra</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesołowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pygmaeus</i> Wesołowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesołowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesołowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesołowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra certa</i> Wesołowska & Haddad, 2009	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesołowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra pusilla</i> Wesołowska & van Harten, 1994	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesołowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925) (Fig. 34)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Scytodes flagellata</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIDAE	<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940) (Fig. 35)	1	LC	AE
SICARIIDAE	<i>Loxosceles parramae</i> Newlands, 1981 (Fig. 36)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Loxosceles speluncarum</i> Simon, 1893	5	VU D2	SAE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
STASIMOPIDAE	<i>Stasimopus oculus</i> Pocock, 1897	3	LC	SAE
THERAPHOSIIDAE	<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990 (Fig. 38)	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910) (Fig. 37)	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
THOMISIDAE	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diaea viridipes</i> Strand, 1909 (Fig. 39)	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881) (Fig. 40)	0	LC	C
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883) (Fig. 41)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882 (Fig. 43)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846 (Fig. 42)	0	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Mastidiores</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE

Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve, South Africa

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, L. Wiese² & L.N. Lotz³

¹SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda, dippenaaransie@gmail.com; ²SANSa team member, Eastern Cape, Jeffreys Bay, South Africa, lwiese9@gmail.com; ³National Museum, Bloemfontein, South Africa (retired)

ABSTRACT: As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), surveys were undertaken in the Eastern Cape. In this paper, an annotated species list of spider species sampled from the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve is presented. A total of 48 families represented by 190 species from 133 genera have been recorded. The most species-rich families are the Thomisidae (27 spp.), Araneidae (22 spp.), and Salticidae (19 spp.), with 22 singletons. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species. Eight of the species were not evaluated and five of them are possibly new to science. Eight species are endemic to the Eastern Cape and three are Baviaanskloof endemics. Only one species is of special concern and three species are endemic to the reserve. Six species are Data Deficient and one Endangered but 92.1% of the species have a wide distribution with no known threats and are listed as Least Concern. **Keywords:** biodiversity, conservation assessment, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

Spiders have been sampled from 195 sites in the Eastern Cape, as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) but large areas still need to be sampled. A total of 837 species, 38.6% of all South African species, have been recorded from the province so far.

We report here on the first SANSa survey on the spider fauna of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (BMR). It is a protected area in the Eastern Cape province and was declared a World Heritage Site in 2004 and is one of the richest plant regions in the world. The BMR includes a cluster of formally protected areas managed by the Eastern Cape Parks Board totaling around 5 530 000 hectares. It includes the Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve, the Groendal Nature Reserve, and Formosa Nature Reserve, as well as private land.

A checklist of the 190 species is presented with information on the global distribution, endemism, and conservation status of each of the species recorded.

METHODS

Study area: The Baviaanskloof, or “Valley of Baboons”, is a 75-km long valley, of varying width, that lies between the parallel east-west running Baviaanskloof and Kouga mountain ranges in the western region of the Eastern Cape province (33°30'S 24°8'E). The eastern-most point of the valley is some 95 km north-west of the coastal city of Port Elizabeth, and its most southerly point is 50 km from the Indian Ocean (Fig. 4). Baviaanskloof is remarkable in terms of the diversity of its natural ecosystems. Seven of South Africa's eight biomes are represented here including Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, Succulent Karoo, Nama-karoo, sub-tropical thicket and savanna. On the northern slopes are the Spekboomveld and Valley Bushveld. On the southern slopes flourishes the Cape Fynbos and in the valleys there is a concentrated of Knysna Forest vegetation. On the mountain plateaus are the Rhinoceros Veldt and Grassland. The widespread succulent Karoo bush in the valley is probably why the Baviaanskloof is classified as a part of the Little Karoo (Figs 1–3).

Surveys, identification, photography, and voucher specimens: Several surveys were undertaken in the BMR. The second author (LW), with members of the Spider Club of Southern Africa, as well as members of the public participating in a SANSa survey during the Easter weekend in 2008, sampled more than 500 specimens. LW paid a second visit to the area sampling and photographing spiders. Collected specimens of both trips were identified in Pretoria by the

Figures 1–3. Different vegetation types found at the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. Photo credits: 1. From web. 2 & 3. Linda Wiese.

first author and voucher specimens are housed at the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. The third author (LL) surveyed the area in February (2008) and the identified voucher specimens are housed in the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

Figure 4: Map of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. After Htoni.

Endemicity: The endemicity values for each species are provided in Appendix 1 based on their currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised:

- 6 – known only from BMR.
- 5 – endemic to the Eastern Cape province (ECE) but wider than the type locality.
- 4 – endemic to South Africa (SAE) but known from only two adjoining provinces.
- 3 – South African endemic (SAE) known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining.
- 2 – endemic to Southern Africa (STHE).
- 1 – endemic to the Afrotropical Region (AE).
- 0 – cosmopolitan, Africa and wider.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 48 families represented by 190 species from 133 genera have been recorded (Table 1). Eight species could not be identified to species level as their taxonomy is unresolved or they could be new to science (Table 2, Appendix 1).

The 190 species collected fall within the range of species reported from other Eastern Cape areas such as the 132 spp. from Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011), 151 spp. from Jeffreys Bay (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023) and 276 spp. from the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Family diversity: The most species-rich families are the Thomisidae (27 spp.), Araneidae (22 spp.), and Salticidae (19 spp.) with 23 families known from only a single species. The same three families were also the most species rich in the three surveys mentioned above.

Conservation status: Of the 190 species sampled, six species (3.2%) are data deficient (DD), i.e., lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while eight species (4.2%) were not evaluated (NE) (Table 2; Appendix 1) of which six might be new to science. The majority of the species (175 spp., 92.1%) are listed as being of least concern (LC). Only the zodariid *Procydrela precursor* Jocqué, 1999 is presently listed as Endangered due to restricted distribution.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (BMR) with total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.) sampled.

FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.	FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	2	Nephilidae	1	2
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Oonopidae	1	1
Araneidae	14	22	Oxyopidae	3	10
Bemmeridae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Caponiidae	1	1	Philodromidae	4	6
Cheiracanthiidae	2	3	Pholcidae	2	3
Clubionidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	1	2
Corinnidae	2	2	Pisauridae	7	7
Ctenidae	1	1	Salticidae	12	19
Cyatholipidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Dictynidae	2	2	Selenopidae	1	3
Deinopidae	1	1	Sicariidae	1	1
Eresidae	1	1	Sparassidae	1	1
Euagridae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	1
Galliellidae	1	2	Tetragnathidae	2	6
Gnaphosidae	7	13	Theraphosidae	1	1
Hahniidae	1	1	Theridiidae	6	7
Linyphiidae	3	3	Thomisidae	15	27
Lycosidae	8	10	Trachelidae	3	3
Migidae	2	2	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Mimetidae	2	2	Uloboridae	4	4
Miturgidae	1	1	Zodariidae	4	4
Mysmenidae	1	1	Zoropsidae	2	2
			48	133	190

Species endemicity: A large percentage of species have a wide distribution and 72 species (37.9%) are African endemics (Table 2) and a total of 21 species (11.1%) are found wider than Africa. Thirty-three species are Southern African endemics but the largest number of species (57) recorded are endemic to South Africa.

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (BMR).

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO SPP.	%
Not Evaluated (NE)	9	4.7
Data Deficient (DD)	6	3.2
Least Concern (LC)	174	91.6
Endangered	1	0.5
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	21	11.1
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	72	37.9
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	32	16.8
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	34	17.8
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	15	7.9
5 – Eastern Cape endemics (ECE)	5	2.6
6 – Known only from type locality BMR	3	1.5

Eight species are Eastern Cape endemics: *Zelotes resolution* FitzPatrick, 2007 (Gnaphosidae); *Proevippa dregei* (Purcell, 1903), *Trabea nigriceps* Purcell, 1903 (Lycosidae); *Anyphops schoenlandi* (Pocock, 1902) (Selenopidae) and *Stasimopus schoenlandi* Pocock, 1900 (Stasimopidae). Three species are endemic to the BMR: *Cheiramiona baviaan* Lotz, 2015, *Drassodella baviaans* Mbo & Haddad, 2019 (Fig. 8) and *D. trilineata* Mbo & Haddad, 2019. All three species are known only from one sex and due to the restricted range listed as Data Deficient.

CONCLUSION

Each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. The contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the BMR and SANParks for the permits and Prof. Charles Haddad for the identification of the Salticidae and Ruan Booysen for the Scytodidae.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–277.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HAMER M. & HADDAD C.R. 2011. Spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the vegetation layer of the Mkam-bati Nature Reserve, Eastern Cape, South Africa. *Koedoe* 53 (1), Art. #1058, 10 pages. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v53i1.1058>.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., WIESE L., FOORD S.H. & HADDAD C.R. 2020. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Addo Elephant National Park in the Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 62(1), a1578. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v62i1.1578>.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., SETHUSA T. & RAIMONDO D. 2020. The South African National Red List of spiders: Patterns, threats, and conservation. *Journal of Arachnology* 48: 110–118.
- LOTZ L.N. 2015. New species of the Afrotropical spider genus *Cheiramiona* Lotz & Dippenaar-Schoeman (Araneae: Eutichuridae). *Zootaxa* 3981(1): 71–94. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.3981.1.3.
- MBO Z. & HADDAD C.R. 2019. A revision of the endemic South African long-jawed ground spider genus *Drassodella* Hewitt, 1916 (Araneae: Gallieniellidae). *Zootaxa* 4582(1): 1–62. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.4582.1.1.
- WIESE L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. SANSa Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa. *SANSa Newsletter* 45: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831510>.

Figures 5–8. Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. 5–7. New species. 5. *Clubiona* sp. (Clubionidae). 6. *Spiroctenus* sp. (Bemmeridae). 7. *Philodromus* sp. (Philodromidae). Baviaanskloof endemic. 8. *Drassodella baviaans*. (Gallieniellidae). Photo credits: Linda Wiese.

Figures 9–23. Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. 9. *Pararaneus perforatus* (Araneidae). 10. *Cheiramiona baviaan* (Cheiracanthiidae). 11. *Clubiona* sp. (Clubionidae). 12. *Scytodes elizabethae* (Scytodidae). 13. *Ctenus pulchriventris* (Ctenidae). 14. *Drassodella baviaans* (Gallieniellidae). 15. *Pardosa manubriata* (Lycosidae). 16. *Pardosa crassipalpis* (Lycosidae). Oxyopidae: 17. *Oxyopes flavipalpis*. 18. *Oxyopes russo*. 19. *Peucetia nicolae*. Philodromidae: 20. *Philodromus brachycephalus*. 21. *Thanatus vulgaris*. 22. *Vidole capensis* (Phyxelididae). 23. *Cispius kimbius* (Pisauridae). Photo credits: Linda Wiese.

Figures 24–38. Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. Salticidae: 24. *Heliophanus hastatus*. 25. *Heliophanus modicus*. Thomisidae: 26. *Holopelus almiae*. 27. *Thomisus australis*. 28. *Thomisus daradioides*. 29. *Runcinia aethiops*. 30. *Synema diana*. 31. *Synema mandibulare*. 32. *Xysticus havilandi*. 33. *Tetragnatha bogotensis* (Tetragnathidae). Zoropsidae: 34. *Griswoldia urbensis*. 35. *Phanotea xhosa*. Uloboridae: 36. *Zosis geniculata*. 37. *Uloborus* sp. new. 38. *Isela okuncana* (Mysmenidae). Photo credits: 24–37. Linda Wiese. 38. Leon Lotz.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), and country endemism (CEND).

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Agelenidae	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Benoitia raymondeae</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
Amaurobiidae	<i>Pseudauximus</i> sp.*		NE	
Araneidae	<i>Araneus apricus</i> (Karsch, 1884)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE
	<i>Gasteracantha versicolor</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Gea infuscata</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ideocaira triquetra</i> Simon, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nemoscolus elongatus</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona novella</i> (Simon, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
	<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C
<i>Pararaneus perforatus</i> (Thorell, 1899) (Fig. 9)	1	LC	AE	
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
Bemmeridae	<i>Spiroctenus</i> sp.* (Fig. 6 & 12)		NE	
Caponiidae	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona baviaan</i> Lotz, 2015 (Fig. 10)	6	DD	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona filipes</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona</i> sp.* (Figs 5 & 11)		NE	
Corinnidae	<i>Coenoptychus tropicalis</i> (Haddad, 2004)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE
Ctenidae	<i>Ctenus pulchriiventris</i> (Simon, 1897) (Fig. 13)	2	LC	STHE
Cyatholipidae	<i>Cyatholipus quadrimaculatus</i> Simon, 1894	4	LC	SAE
Cyrtoucheniidae	<i>Ancylotrypa</i> sp.*		NE	
Deinopidae	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
Dictynidae	<i>Archeodictyna</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Mashimo leleupi</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE
Eresidae	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE
Euagridae	<i>Allothelie australis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	4	LC	SAE
Gallieniellidae	<i>Drassodella baviaans</i> Mbo & Haddad, 2019 (Fig. 14)	6	DD	SAE
	<i>Drassodella trilineata</i> Mbo & Haddad, 2019	6	DD	SAE
Gnaphosidae	<i>Ammoxenus pentheri</i> Simon, 1896	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Asemesthes reflexus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Camillina biplagia</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Trephopoda kannemeyeri</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Xerophaeus appendiculatus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus communis</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes albanicus</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes invidus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes resolution</i> FitzPatrick, 2007	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
Hahniidae	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
Linyphiidae	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Typhistes gloriosus</i> Jocqué, 1984	3	LC	SAE
Lycosidae	<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Arctosa nivosa</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna bimaculata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903 (Fig. 16)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa biampliata</i> (Purcell, 1903) (Fig. 15)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa dregei</i> (Purcell, 1903)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Trabea nigriceps</i> Purcell, 1903	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
Migidae	<i>Moggridgea peringueyi</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Poecilomigas abrahami</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889)	2	LC	STHE
Mimetidae	<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE
Miturgidae	<i>Parapostenus hewitti</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE
Mysmenidae	<i>Isela okuncana</i> Griswold, 1985 (Fig.38)	4	DD	SAE
Nephilidae	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE
Oonopidae	<i>Australoonops granulatus</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE
Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa rostrifrons</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858) (Fig. 17)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940 (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes</i> morpho sp. 3		NE	
	<i>Peucetia maculifera</i> Pocock, 1900	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Peucetia nicolae</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994 (Fig. 19)	3	LC	SAE
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
Philodromidae	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952 (Fig. 20)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.* (Fig. 7)		NE	
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870 (Fig. 21)	0	LC	C
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana vidal</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Smeringopus ubicki</i> Huber, 2012	4	LC	SAE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900) (Fig. 22)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Vidole schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1904)	3	LC	SAE
Pisauridae	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cispus kimbius</i> Blandin, 1978 (Fig. 23)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euprosthénopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Maypaciús bilineatus</i> (Pavesi, 1895)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nilus massajae</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Brancus mustelus</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986 (Fig. 24)	1	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Massagris mirifica</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstaecker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 14)	3	LC
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops braunsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops schoenlandi</i> (Pocock, 1902)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1896)	3	LC	SAE
Sicariidae	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
Sparassidae	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
Stasimopidae	<i>Stasimopus schoenlandi</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DD	SAE
Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C
	<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C
	<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira tigrina</i> Ausserer, 1875	4	LC	SAE
Theridiidae	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus cinctus</i> Blackwall, 1865	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
	<i>Platnickina mneon</i> (Bösenberg & Strand, 1906)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Vidole schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1904)	3	LC	SAE	
Pisauridae	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cispius kimbius</i> Blandin, 1978	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Euprostenopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Maypacijs bilineatus</i> (Pavesi, 1895)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Nilus massajae</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
Salticidae	<i>Brancus mustelus</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE	
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hyllus argyrotexus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Massagris mirifica</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops braunsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops schoenlandi</i> (Pocock, 1902)	5	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1896)	3	LC	SAE	
Sicariidae	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE	
Sparassidae	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE	
Stasimopidae	<i>Stasimopus schoenlandi</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DD	SAE	
Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865 (Fig. 33)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C	
	<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	
Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira tigrina</i> Ausserer, 1875	4	LC	SAE	
Theridiidae	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Latrodectus cinctus</i> Blackwall, 1865	0	LC	C	
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Platnickina mneon</i> (Bösenberg & Strand, 1906)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C	
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Thomisidae	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Geraesta congoensis</i> (Lessert, 1943)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Holopelus almiae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986 (Fig. 26)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> (Lucas, 1846)	0	LC	C
	<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901) (Fig. 29)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
	<i>Runcinia johnstoni</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Simorcus cotti</i> Lessert, 1936	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema diana</i> (Audouin, 1826) (Fig. 30)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema mandibulare</i> Dahl, 1907 (Fig. 31)	2	LC	AE
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957 (Fig. 27)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890 (Fig. 28)	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus natalensis</i> Lessert, 1925	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xysticus havilandi</i> Lawrence, 1942 (Fig. 32)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xysticus tugelanus</i> Lawrence, 1942	2	LC	STHE
Trachelidae	<i>Afroceto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Capobula montana</i> Haddad, Jin, Platnick & Booysen, 2021	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Fuchiba capensis</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	4	LC	SAE
Trochanteriidae	<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1887)	1	LC	AE
Uloboridae	<i>Hyptiotes akermani</i> Wiehle, 1964	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Miagrammopes longicaudus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zosis geniculata</i> (Olivier, 1789) (Fig. 36)	1	LC	C
Zodariidae	<i>Uloborus</i> *sp. new (Fig. 37)		NE	
	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cydrela</i> sp.*		NE	
	<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
Zoropsidae	<i>Procydrela procurator</i> Jocqué, 1999	4	EN	SAE
	<i>Griswoldia urbensis</i> (Lawrence, 1942) (Fig. 34)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Phanotea xhosa</i> Griswold, 1994 (Fig. 35)	4	LC	SAE